

USING MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING ENGLISH FOR PRESCHOOL LEARNERS

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Abstract. When approaching any lesson with young learners you should always consider how old they are, how much prior second language experience they have and their interests. You should consider what is being taught and how you can make it familiar to them. This article describe about using modern technologies in teaching English for preschool learners.

Key words: preschool learners, modern technologies, flashcards, hot potato.

Getting ESL students in kindergarten to sit down and actually learn the language can be a challenge. Yet this energy they have can be channeled into some fun activities for English Class in Kindergarten. At the heart of my concept of using modern educational technologies in English lessons and after school, I use the principles and methods of competence based education, technologies of personal-oriented and developmental learning, and actively use strategies and techniques for teaching semantic reading and working with text. Taking into account the fact that classes often have pupils with different levels of language training in each of their lessons, I use several modern educational technologies:

- ✓ information-communication,
- ✓ project method,
- ✓ pupils ' research activities,
- ✓ multi-level training,
- ✓ differentiated training,
- ✓ collaborative learning technology or group work,
- ✓ health-saving technologies.

Due to the fact that each class immediately highlights differences in the level

of learning among pupils, the most acceptable and relevant in the organization of the educational process is the technology of intra-class differentiation with the addition of elements of multi-level learning. Taking into account the typological features of each pupil, I divide the class into conditional groups "A", "B", "C". I use techniques of teamwork, for dynamic pairs or groups. Tasks of group "C" are fixed as the basic standard — minimal or reproductive. Here I highlight the multiplicity of repetition, teach you to allocate lexical supports. Tasks " B " are built on an analytical and synthetic level and provide the mental activity that is necessary to solve tasks for use. Job group "A" assume the creative or production level. Pupils consciously and creatively apply their knowledge by making mini-dialogues and monologues on the topic. Elements of the organization of the group form of work allow me to activate the cognitive activity of pupils in the classroom, to include each pupil in the learning process. Within the groups, everyone can Express their opinion, actively participate in the decision of educational programs, in accordance with the level of language training, studied lexical units. For each lesson, I create didactic material of different complexity. All this gives a tangible educational result.

Flashcards. As an ESL teacher, the chances are you're already pretty familiar with flashcards. They are absolute gold to use with ESL classes of any age. Whether you're breaking topics down into bite size pieces or using flashcards as a useful tool to memorise key vocabulary, they make such a fun and easy activity.

Fishing for words. Another great vocabulary activity is letting your children fish for words. For this activity, it's best if you have a specific topic in mind. If you're learning some specific vocabulary or want to focus on some tricky words appropriate for kindergarten children, this activity is perfect. It requires a little more preparation than some other activities, but the learning potential and fun are well worth it.

Hot potato. Start this fun activity by putting some music or a timer on. Start passing around a ball or another object around the room. When the music stops, the person holding the hot potato has to do something. You could get them to say a word

they've learnt that day, or say a full sentence. This is really fast-paced and fun for your kindergarten children to do.

Using fun activities in your English class for kindergarten is so important to keep children engaged and willing to learn. We hope you like our ideas for the best ESL games for Kindergarten and find something new and engaging to do with your little ones. Let us know in the comments if you have any of your own fantastic ideas to use when teaching young children how to speak English.

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